

Associations Between the Mortality Trends by Cause of Death and Hazardous Alcohol Consumption in Russia. The “Conveyor Belt Effect” in Action?

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Abstract

Relevance. Alcohol consumption is detrimental to the Russian population health and contributes significantly to mortality. The aim of the study is to determine the associations between alcohol consumption and mortality by cause of death in Russia.

Data and methods. Data from the Russian Fertility and Mortality Database (RusFMD) were used. Correlation analysis of time series was used to estimate the statistical association with indicators of hazardous alcohol consumption for 80 causes of death.

Findings and Discussion. Associations were found for 30 causes of death in classes such as diseases of the circulatory system, neoplasms, diseases of the digestive system, external and unspecified causes of death, infectious diseases, diseases of the respiratory system, and diseases of the nervous system. After pre-testing, the analyses were performed with a zero lag.

Correlations have been found for a number of chronic diseases for which it is difficult to explain a direct response to variations in alcohol consumption. We suggest a ‘conveyor belt effect’; there is a vulnerable group in the population (at-risk population) whose health is compromised by high alcohol consumption. Mortality in this group will respond immediately to variations in current consumption. At normal levels of consumption, the ‘lethal conveyor belt’ carries these individuals to the fatal line at a certain speed, which may accelerate or decelerate as consumption increases or decreases. The frequency of binge drinking or other hazardous drinking patterns, combined with changes in behaviour, including disruption of treatment, can have a particularly strong effect on the speed of the conveyor belt.

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Keywords

Alcohol-related mortality, public health, causes of death, risk factor

JEL codes: I12, I18, I1

Introduction

Excessive alcohol consumption causes significant damage to public health and public safety, being an important factor in premature mortality, morbidity, injuries, accidents, crime, homicide, suicide, and other socio-demographic problems (Laramée et al. 2015; Westman et al. 2015; Borges et al. 2017; Abdul-Rahman et al. 2018). It contributes most to the mortality of working-age men (Shkolnikov et al. 2002; Zaridze et al. 2009b; Zhao et al. 2023).

Despite the successful implementation of an anti-alcohol policy in Russia over the past decade and a half (Neufeld and Rehm 2013), alcoholisation rates in Russia are still high. For example, according to the Ministry of Health of Russia's Order dated 30.07.2019 (Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation 2019), 57% of alcohol consumption in 2022 was vodka and other hard liquors. In addition, unregistered consumption accounts for one third of the total consumption (Rosstat EMISS 2024a, 2024b), including that of alcoholic surrogates, such as alcohol containing liquids not intended for use as alcoholic beverages and home-made alcohol (Radaev 2016; Loskutnikova et al. 2019; Korotayev et al. 2024). Studies show the hazardous drinking behaviours (surrogate consumption, binge drinking, persistently high consumption of hard liquor) are most closely associated with mortality in Russia and other Eastern European countries (Khalturina and Korotayev 2006; Leon et al. 2007; Tomkins et al. 2007; Treisman 2010; Kueng and Yakovlev 2016; Korotayev et al. 2018) and other regions (Rehm and Hasan 2020). Furthermore, the tense situation with alcohol consumption in Russia is characterised by a high prevalence of the alcohol dependence syndrome (alcoholism) and alcoholic psychoses (World Health Organization 2018). In turn, the incidence of alcoholic psychosis is considered to be one of the relatively reliable indicators of alcoholisation of the population because such incidents are often accompanied by an emergency call, following which the patient receives public health care, and the diagnosis is reflected in official statistics.

The short nomenclature of causes of death used by Rosstat includes 17 causes of death directly attributable to alcohol, all of which have the word 'alcohol' in their titles (Table 1).

In the above causes of death, alcohol is the primary medical diagnosis leading to death. However, these causes represent only a fraction of all causes of death directly or indirectly related to hazardous drinking.

Most alcohol-related deaths belong to the class of external causes (accidents, suicide, homicide) and are often hidden behind somatic, formally non-alcoholic causes (Nemtsov, 2009). Although alcohol is directly referred to in 46 causes of death according to the most detailed four-digit ICD-10 classification, the number of causes of death etiologically attributable to alcohol exceeds 200 (World Health Organization 2018).

Table 1. Causes of death directly attributable to alcohol as per the Rosstat summary nomenclature of causes of death and their respective ICD-10 coding

ICD-10 Chapter	Title and ICD code of the cause of death
Mental and behavioural disorders	dependence syndrome caused by alcohol use (F10.2)
	harmful use of alcohol (F10.1)
	acute intoxication with alcohol (F10)
Mental and behavioural disorders; diseases of the nervous system	other and unspecified mental and behavioural disorders due to use of alcohol (other, from F10-F19)
	psychotic disorder, encephalopathy, dementia (F10.5, G31.2, F00-F03)
Diseases of the nervous system	degeneration of nervous system due to alcohol (G31.2)
	alcoholic polyneuropathy (G62.1)
Diseases of the circulatory system	alcoholic myopathy (G72.1)
	alcoholic cardiomyopathy (I42.6)
Diseases of the digestive system	alcoholic liver disease (K70)
	alcohol-induced acute pancreatitis (K85.2)
	alcohol-induced chronic pancreatitis (K86)
Congenital malformations, deformations, and chromosomal abnormalities	alcoholic gastritis (K29.2)
	foetal alcohol syndrome (Q86)
External causes of morbidity and mortality	accidental poisoning by alcohol (X45)
	intentional self-poisoning by and exposure to alcohol (X65)
	poisoning by and exposure to alcohol, undetermined intent (Y15)

Source: Rosstat, 2010 Summary Nomenclature of Causes of Death, based on the International Statistical Classification of Diseases and Health-Related Problems, X Revision.

The association between mortality from various causes and alcohol is established by epidemiological studies or by meta-analysis summarizing the results of many epidemiological studies. These studies estimate the relative risk of death of individuals according to the level and/or patterns of their alcohol consumption (Leon et al. 2007; Zaridze et al. 2009a; Rehm et al. 2017). For Russia, there are several relative risk estimates that characterise an increased risk of death due to heavy alcohol consumption, both for all causes of death and for many individual causes of death, including cardiovascular diseases (Leon et al. 2007; Zaridze et al. 2009a). The attributable fraction method estimates the proportions of alcohol-related mortality by combining epidemiological estimates of relative risk with data on the distribution of alcohol consumption in the population (Candari et al. 2017).

According to a recent assessment by P.O. Kuznetsova (2020), 11% of all deaths in Russia (196 thousand) were caused by alcohol in 2018. The proportions of alcohol-attributable deaths for men and women were 16.3% (146.000) and 5.5% (50.000), respectively. According to the international Global Burden of Disease project, in 2021, 5% (118 thousand) of all Russian deaths (91 thousand, or 8% among men and 27 thousand, or 2% among women) were caused by alcohol (Global Burden... 2025).

It is possible, however, that estimates based on epidemiological and consumption data underestimate the contribution of alcohol to the level and especially the trends of mortality and life expectancy in Russia and other Eastern European countries. This is indicated by the analysis of the unexpectedly sharp and large-scale fluctuations in mortality in Russia due to ‘natural experiments’ such as the 1985 anti-alcohol campaign, the dramatic increase in the economic and physical availability of alcohol in 1992–1994, and the strict measures to regulate the alcohol market in 2005–2007 (Leon et al. 1997; Shkolnikov et al. 1998; McKee et al. 2001; Shkolnikov et al. 2001, 2013). The anti-alcohol campaign of the 1980s was followed by a sharp fall in mortality, and the ‘return’ of alcohol in the early 1990s, by its sharp increase, and the restrictive measures of the mid-2000s, by its significant reduction. All these variations were clear deviations from long-term mortality trends.

In an important study by J. Rehm and colleagues (2023), a direct comparison was made between the reduction in mortality actually observed in Lithuania after a sharp increase in alcohol excise taxes in 2017 and model estimates based on the attributable fraction method. The analysis showed that the real reduction in mortality exceeded the expected (model estimate) by 63%. Therefore, it appears that estimates of alcohol-related mortality based on epidemiological data on relative risks of death and alcohol consumption may not fully reflect the population mortality response.

Other examples from the literature of inconsistencies between changes in mortality and epidemiological assumptions about the impact of alcohol on the individual relate to the time intervals between variations in consumption and changes in mortality. In particular, there have been cases of rapid reduction in liver cirrhosis mortality immediately following the introduction of alcohol rationing or alcohol policy measures (Corrao et al. 1997; Edwards 1997; Norström and Skog 2001; Chrystoja et al. 2020; Zatoński et al. 2020). These cases contradict the concept of this disease slowly developing as a result of years of high-dose alcohol consumption. Mortality from cardiovascular and many other chronic diseases in Russia has experienced significant fluctuations, strictly mirroring the drop in alcohol consumption during the anti-alcohol campaign of 1985–1988 and the sharp increase in consumption in 1992–1994 (Leon et al. 1997, 2009, 2010).

What is the explanation for these contradictions? In fact, the dependence of population mortality on alcoholisation is not reducible to the dependence of the risk of death on alcohol consumption at the individual level. The integral impact of alcohol on the population is modified by structural and social factors (Norström and Skog 2001). For this reason, there may be a seeming inconsistency between patterns at the individual level and empirically observed variations in population mortality.

In this regard, monitoring observed variations in mortality and life expectancy and analysing the statistical relationships of these variations with the characteristics of alcohol consumption and alcoholisation of the population are of particular importance. In 1994, the first Russian analysis of this kind was published in the newspaper *Izvestia*, which demonstrated a high negative correlation ($r = 0.97$) between life expectancy and mortality from alcohol poisoning in Russia in the 1970s–1990s (Nemtsov and Shkolnikov 1994; Shkolnikov et al. 2019). It should be borne in mind that alcohol poisoning deaths then and now account for only 1–2% of the standardised all-cause mortality rate, and their direct contribution to population life expectancy is low. A recent study found that the loss of life expectancy from all directly alcohol-related causes of death, of which poisoning accounts for about a quarter (27% in 2020), is currently about half a year (Zamyatnina 2022). Therefore, the high corre-

lation indicates the association of life expectancy with alcoholisation of the population as a factor affecting health and mortality from many causes.

A more detailed analysis of the correlations between the time series of mortality rates and life expectancy on the one hand and alcohol consumption and alcoholisation on the other was carried out in more recent studies (Nemtsov et al. 2019; Danilova et al. 2020). These studies confirmed the previously established high negative correlation of life expectancy with alcohol poisoning mortality, along with its slight weakening in the second half of the 2000s and 2010s.

In the present study, we identify a list of specific causes of death empirically associated with alcohol. This is done by systematically analysing alcohol-related mortality correlations, using a much more detailed list of causes of death than the previous studies, and using more up-to-date data from 1999 to 2021. In this way, we empirically identify the range of diseases and conditions that correlate with exposure to alcohol.

Data and methods

Data from the Russian Database on Births and Deaths (RusFMD) were used in our analyses. They represent mortality rates (per 1,000,000 person-years) by sex, five-year age groups and causes of death according to the Rosstat and Ministry of Health summary nomenclatures in effect in 1999-2010 and then since 2011. The choice of this timeframe was determined by two considerations. Firstly, the Russian nomenclatures in these years consistently corresponded to ICD-10, which ensured good comparability of data over time. Secondly, these years saw significant variations in the level and structure of alcohol consumption (Nemtsov and Razvodovsky 2017; Radaev and Roschina 2019, 2021). Consumption increased between 1999 and 2003, then reduced rapidly (probably due to the alcohol market regulation measures of 2005-2007), and then the rate of reduction slowed down significantly. Such non-monotonic variations depending on population behaviour and alcohol policy provide good empirical material for measuring the statistical relationship between mortality and alcohol consumption.

To construct a continuous time series of causes of death from 1999 to 2021, the 1999 and 2011 short nomenclatures were compared. The causes of death in each of the nomenclatures were grouped so that their contents were identical (or almost identical with minimal differences) throughout the time series. A list of 80 causes of death was obtained for further analysis. These included causes of death from the classes of neoplasms, diseases of the respiratory system, diseases of the circulatory system, diseases of the digestive system, external causes, and unspecified causes (see Table A1 and Table A2 in the Annex).

The level of mortality from selected causes was measured by a standardised death rate (SDR), free from the influence of the time-dependent age structure of the population. Age-specific mortality rates by sex, age, and cause of death from RusFMD and the 2013 European Standard for Age Structure of Population were used to calculate the SDR (European standard population ESP2013).

SDRs by causes of death were calculated separately for men and women in the age intervals 15-64 years¹ and 65+ (65 years and older). In the 1980s-2000s, variations in total

¹ It should be noted that the sale of alcohol is legally permitted in Russia to persons aged 18 and older, but in reality, alcohol consumption often occurs at earlier ages, in particular at age 13-16 (Skvortsova and Babyshkina 2023).

mortality and life expectancy in Russia were determined mainly by working-age mortality, which, in turn, was strongly influenced by the fluctuations in alcohol consumption (Leon et al. 2009, 2010; Shkolnikov et al. 2013). These ages have the highest proportion of causes of death directly attributable to alcohol (Zamyatnina 2022). In contrast, degenerative diseases closely linked to accumulated risks and ageing are much more significant at older ages. The specific boundaries of ‘working age’ and ‘older age’ (15 years and 65 years) were assigned for the purpose of comparability with WHO databases and other international sources.

Estimating the real alcohol consumption by the Russian population is a challenging research task due to the underestimation of consumption in the official data on alcohol retail sales. These data do not include illegally produced and home-produced alcohol, as well as alcohol-containing medical, hygienic and other surrogates not intended for consumption as alcoholic beverages (Loskutnikova et al. 2019; Korotayev et al. 2024). In the 1980s, V. Treml (Treml 1982) proposed one of the first solutions to the problem of calculating unregistered alcohol consumption in the Soviet Union, by using the data on sugar consumption in excess of ‘normal’ per capita consumption, because sugar is used in the production of moonshine. A.V. Nemtsov proposed to estimate real alcohol consumption by using an indirect method based on forensic data on the proportion of deaths with the presence of alcohol in the bloodstream (Nemtsov 2000, 2011).

Currently, according to the methodology for estimating the average per capita consumption of alcohol in the Russian Federation (Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation 2019), the Russian Ministry of Health estimates real alcohol consumption in Russia and in Russian regions using the principal component method and regression analysis. Real alcohol consumption is estimated by using its close association with mortality from alcohol poisoning, incidence of alcoholic psychosis and the life expectancy differential between women and men. Factor loadings indicate the maximum explanatory power of alcohol poisoning mortality.

Given these findings, as well as Russia’s characteristic pattern of hazardous alcohol consumption, including binge drinking, dominance of the vodka, and use of surrogates, we use the SDR from alcohol poisoning and SDR from all 17 causes of death directly attributable to alcohol as indicators of hazardous alcohol consumption.

After obtaining time series of SDRs from the 80 causes of death on the one hand and alcohol indicators on the other, they were transformed into first difference series in order to achieve stationarity (Norström and Skog 2001).

The resulting series of first differences were used to estimate correlations between mortality from various causes and mortality directly attributable to alcohol. To measure the strength of the association, the Spearman’s correlation coefficient was used, which, unlike the usual Pearson’s coefficient, does not imply normal distribution of the variables involved in the analysis or the linear relationship. An association was considered established if the correlation coefficient was statistically significant at the $p < 0.01$ or $p < 0.05$ level. According to the Chaddock scale, the association was considered weak for correlation coefficients below 0.5, moderate for correlation coefficients of 0.5–0.7; and high for correlation coefficients of 0.7–0.9.

The preliminary correlation analysis with lags of different lengths showed that the highest values of correlation coefficients correspond to the zero lag, when the time series are not time-shifted relative to each other. This measures the instantaneous association between variations in hazardous alcohol consumption and mortality from various causes of death.

Findings

The causes of death for which mortality has statistically significant correlations with the SDR from all 17 causes of death directly attributable to alcohol are shown in Table 2. The table does not show correlation coefficients with alcohol poisoning because no significant differences were found between them and the corresponding correlation coefficients with the sum of all directly alcohol-related causes of death (see Table A1 and Table A2 in the Annex). All statistically significant correlations at the $p < 0.05$ level in the table are highlighted in green, with the dark-green standing for the values of correlation coefficients above 0.5, which, according to the Chaddock scale, mean 'moderate' and 'strong' association, while the light-green stand for weak association (coefficient values below 0.5). It is worth noting that these correlations are calculated on the differences between neighbouring years for both time series, i.e. without any time lag, and therefore show an immediate, 'instantaneous' response of mortality to variations in alcohol consumption.

Table 2. Spearman's coefficients for correlations between standardised mortality rates from various causes and standardised mortality rates from causes of death directly attributable to alcohol for men and women aged 15-64 years and 65 years and over#

Class of cause of death	Cause of death	ICD-10 code	Men		Women	
			Age 15-64	Age 65+	Age 15-64	Age 65+
Infectious diseases	Tuberculosis	A15-19, B90	0.605**	0.381	0.674**	-0.081
	Malignant neoplasm of liver and intrahepatic bile ducts	C22	0.108	0.485*	0.440*	0.067
Neoplasms	Malignant melanoma of skin	C43	0.305	0.014	-0.100	0.425*
Diseases of the nervous system	Other disorders of the nervous system	G10-12, G14, G23-25, G31.0,1,8,9; G36-37, G43-45, G47, G50-61, G62.0,2-9; G63-71, G72.0,2-9; G81-91, G93-98	0.636**	0.06	0.476*	-0.228
	Hypertensive heart disease	I11	0.569**	0.404	0.575**	0.26
Diseases of the circulatory system	Recurrent myocardial infarction	I22	0.217	0.450*	0.313	0.346
	Atherosclerotic heart disease	I25.1	0.651**	0.413	0.747**	0.37
	Chronic ischaemic heart disease	I25.2-6,8, I25.9	0.704**	0.627**	0.680**	0.430*

Class of cause of death	Cause of death	ICD-10 code	Men		Women	
			Age 15-64	Age 65+	Age 15-64	Age 65+
Diseases of the circulatory system	Other acute ischaemic heart diseases	I20, I24.1-9	0.807**	0.025	0.836**	-0.158
	Other forms of heart disease	I30-41, I42.0-5,7,8,9; I43-45, I46.0,1,9; I47-49, I51	0.855**	0.461*	0.898**	0.12
	Subarachnoid haemorrhage	I60	0.531*	0.064	0.086	-0.069
	Intracerebral and other non-traumatic intracranial haemorrhages	I61-62	0.687**	0.193	0.663**	-0.118
	Cerebral infarction	I63	0.691**	0.551**	0.840**	0.521*
	Stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction	I64	0.563**	0.336	0.466*	0.37
	Other cerebrovascular diseases	I67-69	0.221	0.686**	0.275	0.544**
Diseases of the respiratory system	Bacterial pneumonia	J13-J15	0.643**	0.228	0.182	-0.104
	Pneumonia, organism unspecified	J18	0.798**	0.414	0.627**	0.159
	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases	J41, J42, J44	0.475*	0.440*	0.181	0.29
	Suppurative and necrotic conditions of lower respiratory tract	J85-86	0.635**	0.078	0.447*	-0.275
Diseases of the digestive system	Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver (excluding alcoholic)	K74	0.861**	0.688**	0.910**	0.589**
	Other diseases of liver	K71-73, K75-76	0.609**	0.168	0.691**	-0.018
	Acute pancreatitis and other diseases of pancreas	K85, K86.1-9	0.781**	0.4	0.845**	0.388
	Other diseases of the digestive system	K00-14, K20-24, K28, K30-31, K57-64, K66, K82-83, K90-93	0.719**	0.431*	0.425*	0.447*
Symptoms, signs and abnormalities	Other ill-defined and unspecified causes of mortality	R00-53, R55-94, R96-99	0.709**	0.555**	0.709**	0.461*

Class of cause of death	Cause of death	ICD-10 code	Men		Women	
			Age 15-64	Age 65+	Age 15-64	Age 65+
External causes of death	Fall	W00-19	0.532*	0.339	0.451*	0.316
	Other and unspecified external causes of death and their sequelae	W20-W31, W35-W64, W85-W99, X10-X30, X32-X39, X50-X57, Y35, Y85-Y871, Y88-Y891	0.345	0.366	0.529*	0.363
		Accidental inhalation and ingestion causing obstruction of respiratory tract	W75-84	0.527*	0.595**	0.356
	Exposure to smoke, fire and flames	X00-09	0.713**	0.584**	0.731**	0.424*
	Homicide (assault, violence)	X85-Y09	0.441**	0.244	0.378	0.424*
	Event with undetermined intent	Y10-34	0.713**	0.485*	0.508*	0.059

Source: authors' calculations. *Note:* Only statistically significant associations are shown. ** (Two-way) correlation is significant at the 0.01 level; * (Two-way) correlation is significant at the 0.05 level; ** (Two-way) correlation is significant at the 0.05 level with all directly alcohol-related causes of death, except alcohol poisoning.

In total, we found an association of alcohol consumption with 30 causes of death out of 80 ones considered, belonging to the following classes of causes of death: circulatory diseases, neoplasms, digestive diseases, respiratory diseases, external and unspecified causes of death, infections, and diseases of the nervous system. For twelve causes of death the association was strong (coefficient of correlation greater than 0.7) for at least one sex and age group (15-64, 65+); for thirteen causes it was moderate (0.5-0.7) and for the remaining five it was weak (below 0.5) but still statistically significant.

Figure 1 shows the apparent similarity between the changes in the SDR from several causes of death not formally related to alcohol and the changes in the SDR from alcohol poisoning between 1999 and 2021.

The strongest association was found between alcohol and 'other heart diseases' (I30-41, I42.0-5,7,8,9; I43-45, I46.0,1,9; I47-49, I51) in women and men of working age, while at the age of 65 and older, the association was statistically insignificant. It should be noted that until 2005, 'other heart diseases' included alcoholic cardiomyopathy (I42.6). Apart from 'other heart diseases', a strong association with alcohol was also found at working age for chronic ischaemic heart disease (I25.2-6,8, I25.9), other forms of acute ischaemic heart disease (I20, 24.1-9), atherosclerotic heart disease (I25.1) and cerebral infarction (I63) (for men, the association was moderate); only mortality from cerebral infarction and chronic

Figure 1. Standardised mortality rates at the age of 15-64 from certain causes of death, Russia, 2000-2021, men and women. *Source:* authors’ calculations.

ischaemic heart disease showed an association with alcohol for both working age and old age in both sexes.

Apart from diseases of the circulatory system, a strong association with alcohol is observed for ‘pneumonia, organism unspecified’ (J18), acute pancreatitis and other diseases of pancreas (K85, K86. 1-9), non-alcoholic cirrhosis, other diseases of the digestive system (K00-14, K20-24, K28, K30-31, K57-64, K66, K82-83, K90-93), ill-defined and unknown causes of death (R00-53, R55-94, R96-99), accidental exposure to smoke, fire and flame (X00-09) and injuries with undetermined intent (Y10-34). Moreover, for a number of these, there is a statistically significant association for both age groups and both sexes.

The causes of death with a moderate association include: tuberculosis (A15-19, B90), other disorders of the nervous system (G10-12, G14, G23-25, G31.0,1,8,9; G36-37, G43-45, G47, G50-61, G62.0,2-9; G63-71, G72.0,2-9; G81-91, G93-98), hypertensive heart disease with predominantly cardiac involvement (I11), subarachnoid haemorrhage (I60), other cerebrovascular diseases (I67-69) (ages 65+ only), bacterial pneumonia (J13-15), suppurative and necrotic conditions of lower respiratory tract (J85-86), other diseases of liver (K71-73, K75-76), fall (W00-19), accidental inhalation and ingestion causing obstruction of respiratory tract (W75-84), other and unspecified external causes of death and sequelae (W20-W31, W35-W64, W85-W99, X10-X30, X32-X39, X50-X57, Y35, Y85-Y871, Y88-Y891).

No statistically significant association with alcohol was found for traffic deaths and suicides. A weak association with homicide was found for men aged 15-64 years and women aged 65+ years.

Discussion

Thirty causes of death have been identified for which fluctuations in mortality rates are statistically significantly associated with fluctuations in hazardous alcohol consumption by the population. These causes of death can be divided into four groups: 1) Causes etiologically related to alcohol, i.e. diseases and conditions in the occurrence and development of which alcohol consumption is an obvious and strong factor (liver cirrhosis, pancreatitis), as per medical knowledge and epidemiologic studies; 2) causes where the influence of alcohol on mortality is less obvious (ischaemic heart disease, tuberculosis); 3) external causes of death, which include accidents and violent causes; and 4) “garbage” causes of death (“unspecified”, “ill-defined”, “miscellaneous”, “other”), where the clinical content is poorly defined.

Alcohol and diseases of the circulatory system

The finding that there is a direct response of mortality from diseases of the circulatory system to alcohol can be considered one of the most important results of our analysis, given the contribution to all-cause mortality and the strength of the association with alcohol: as many as five of the twelve strongly associated causes of death belong to this class.

There is some scientific evidence that hazardous alcohol consumption is associated with an increased risk of death from cardiovascular diseases (Ronksley et al. 2011). For example, there is evidence of a J-shaped relationship between alcohol consumption and the risk of death from ischaemic heart disease, and the scientific debate continues to this day (Roerecke and Rehm 2010; Knott et al. 2015; GBD 2016..., 2018; Zhao et al. 2023). It should be stressed that the hypothetical cardioprotective effect of alcohol only applies to moderate consumption of red wine or beer (Criqui 1996; Constant 1997; Klatsky 2015). However, the cardioprotective effect disappears when a shock dose is consumed over a short period of time even against a background of generally low consumption (Roerecke and Rehm 2010, 2012; Stockwell et al. 2016).

Alcohol consumption is also a significant risk factor for the brain and cerebral blood flow. Even moderate alcohol consumption is associated with adverse effects on the brain (Topiwala et al. 2017). Alcohol consumption is a risk factor for developing arterial hypertension (Fuchs et al. 2001), ischaemic or haemorrhagic stroke (Mazzaglia et al. 2001; Patra et al. 2010). Besides, the risk of stroke increases immediately after consuming a shock dose of alcohol (Sundell et al. 2008; Hillbom et al. 2011).

Alcohol and neoplasms

An association with alcohol has also been found for neoplasms such as liver or intrahepatic bile duct cancer, and a mildly strong association, for cutaneous malignant melanoma. A number of cohort and cross-sectional studies have shown an association of alcohol consumption with an increased risk of developing liver or intrahepatic bile duct cancer (Kuper et al. 2001; Makiuchi et al. 2019; McGee et al. 2019). Two meta-analyses have focused on the relationship between alcohol consumption and the occurrence of cutaneous melanoma (Rota et al. 2014; Bagnardi et al. 2015), and they all indicate a positive association, although not a strong one, and also suggest a dose-dependent increase in risk (Gandini et al. 2018).

Alcohol, diseases of the digestive system, and a statistical artefact

A very close association has been found for several diseases of the digestive system, including non-alcoholic liver cirrhosis and fibrosis, other hepatic diseases, acute pancreatitis, and other diseases of pancreas. The association of alcohol with non-alcoholic cirrhosis and fibrosis may be due to the fact that in some cases alcoholic cirrhosis is registered as non-alcoholic on the medical certificate of death (Rehm and Shield 2019). This may be due to possible difficulties in identifying the alcoholic genesis of the liver changes during macroscopic and microscopic examination by a specialist and their access to the medical history of the deceased, which may have diagnosed alcoholism. In addition, due to the nature of the mortality data used, alcohol-related pancreatitis was included with other chronic pancreatitis in our study until 2005, which may also contribute to the association between this cause of death and alcohol consumption.

However, the association of mortality from diseases of the digestive system with alcohol may not be due solely to an artefact (error in coding the cause of death), as the effect of alcohol consumption on the development of non-alcoholic liver or pancreatic diseases has been extensively studied (Irving et al. 2009; Rehm et al. 2010; Samokhvalov et al. 2015; Llamosas-Falcón et al. 2024).

Alcohol, respiratory diseases, and social marginalisation

Alcohol increases the risk of developing community-acquired pneumonia, according to systematic reviews (Simou et al. 2018a); a monotonic positive dose – response relationship was also observed (Samokhvalov et al. 2010). Alcohol abuse is also a factor that increases the risk of death from pneumococcal infection (Chen et al. 2021). The presence of alcohol use disorders in patients with community-acquired pneumococcal pneumonia has been associated with a longer length of stay in hospital, higher in-patient costs and an increased risk of death (Gili-Miner et al. 2015).

Mortality trends in tuberculosis, a socially significant infectious lung disease, also show a strong association with alcohol. Systematic reviews have shown that alcohol abuse significantly affects both the incidence and outcome of tuberculosis (Rehm et al. 2009) and increases the risks of relapse and death in TB patients (Weiangkham et al. 2022). Every additional 10-20g of alcohol per day increases the risk of tuberculosis by 12% (Simou et al. 2018b). J. Rehm et al. (2009) point to increased risks of both contracting tuberculosis and hazardous alcohol consumption among marginalised groups. Describing the increase in mortality among Russia's working-age population in the 2000s, V. Semyonova and co-authors also note that mortality from causes such as tuberculosis and community-acquired pneumonia is more characteristic of “socially maladapted or dysadapted individuals” (Semenova et al. 2009).

Alcohol and external causes of death, including injuries with undetermined intent

Given that Russia has a very high proportion of deaths from external causes with blood alcohol detected – 46% in 2022 (Zamyatnina et al. 2023), the close association between mortality from this class of causes of death and trends in alcohol consumption was to be expected. Indeed, we found statistically significant associations of mortality from causes of death directly

attributable to alcohol with mortality from accidental falls, homicide, accidental inhalation and ingestion causing obstruction of the respiratory tract.

Our analysis found no strong association of alcohol with external causes of death such as suicide, accidental drowning, and traffic accidents. Only weak correlations with alcohol were found for homicide among men aged 15-64 and women aged 65+. This result is rather unexpected, as the risk of death from these causes is increased by alcohol at the individual level, which has been repeatedly found by Russian and international studies, including meta-reviews (Alpert et al. 2022; Taylor et al. 2010; Asgarian et al. 2019; Hamilton et al. 2018; Kuhns et al. 2014; Panczak et al. 2013; Amiri and Behnezhad 2020; Isaacs et al. 2022; Borges et al. 2017). There may be significant under-reporting of those external causes that are considered socially significant or targeted by the relevant government agencies or sponsored programmes. In particular, it is highly likely that official statistics significantly underestimate mortality due to homicide, suicide, and some other external causes by shifting deaths from these causes to the category of “injury with undetermined intent” (Andreev et al. 2015; Vasin 2015; Davidovsky et al. 2017; Puchnina 2018). The proportion of SDR from this cause among other external causes increased rapidly in the 2000-2010s and has exceeded deaths from homicide and suicide combined since 2014 (Yumaguzin and Vinnik 2019). E.M. Andreev et al. showed how high mortality due to this “garbage” cause of death can be distributed between homicide, suicide, and accidents (Andreev et al. 2015). Some increase in mortality from injuries with undetermined intent has also been observed in other countries (Tøllefsen et al. 2016). Thus, significant variations in registration practices during the observation period are likely to result in longitudinal incomparability of the time series of homicide, suicide, and accidents (e.g. drowning) reducing the analytical value of these data.

The association of traffic deaths with alcohol may have been additionally affected by modifying factors, such as the widespread introduction of continuous video surveillance on the roads and a zero blood alcohol limit for driving, etc., which took place in the 2000-2010s.

Within the class of external causes, the strongest association with alcohol for both sexes and age groups was found for accidents caused by exposure to smoke, fire and flames. This is in line with the findings of the Russian Emergencies Ministry, according to which three quarters of all fire victims in the country are attributable to fires caused by people under the influence of alcohol (Pis'mo MCHS Rossii... 2019). Alcohol consumption is also known to contribute to significantly longer hospital stays for burn patients (Lumenta et al. 2008).

Alcohol and “garbage” causes of death

Our analysis showed an association of alcohol with deaths from a number of so-called “garbage” causes of death, including other disorders of the nervous system, other heart diseases, other cerebrovascular diseases, other chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases, other diseases of the digestive system, ill-defined and unknown causes of death. This phenomenon may indirectly indicate a systematic tendency to assign alcohol-related deaths to other, non-alcohol-related causes of death. Such a shift is most conveniently done by using imprecisely defined causes with unclear clinical content. It can be assumed that this is facilitated by the stigmatisation of alcohol as a cause of death in Russian society. The association of alcohol with “garbage” causes of death once again illustrates the high latency of alcohol-related mortality in Russia.

Immediate response of mortality by causes of death to alcohol: the “conveyor belt effect”

The rapid response of mortality from all types of accidents, violence and other external causes to alcohol is easy to explain and was to be expected. However, our analysis also revealed zero-lag correlations between variations in mortality from many chronic diseases and variations in hazardous alcohol consumption. These diseases belong to the classes of neoplasms, diseases of the circulatory system, diseases of the respiratory system and diseases of the digestive system. For pathologies such as cardiomyopathy, liver cirrhosis and cancer, diseases of the pancreas, neuropsychiatric diseases, a gradual accumulation of adverse effects of alcohol on the corresponding organs and systems is assumed, which would lead over decades to their fatal degradation and death of the whole organism.

In Introduction, a reference was made to the examples in the literature of variations in mortality from liver cirrhosis and other chronic diseases observed in other countries and in Russia during “natural experiments” that resulted in a sharp decrease or increase in alcohol consumption. This phenomenon may be related to there being a high-risk group in the population, consisting of people whose health has been severely compromised by years of intensive alcohol consumption. Norström and Skog (2001) referred to the group as a “reservoir”. People in the “reservoir” are close to death and their mortality is much more elastic to subsequent increases or decreases in consumption. A significant increase in consumption could dramatically increase mortality in this group and lead as a result to a significant increase in mortality for the whole population from many chronic causes of death.

The normal level of alcohol consumption can be likened to the seemingly constant speed of the conveyor belt that carries people in the “reservoir” to their deaths. An abnormal increase or decrease in consumption is like an acceleration or deceleration of the conveyor belt carrying people to the brink.

We believe that the “conveyor belt effect” may be helpful in understanding the results of our analysis. In Russia, a country with the most dangerous “northern” pattern of alcohol consumption, with high consumption of vodka and strong spirits, frequent consumption of shock doses of alcohol, and even bouts of heavy drinking, the reservoir may represent a significant proportion of the population and the “conveyor belt effect” may be particularly strong.

For people with alcohol-impaired health, drinking shock doses of alcohol can be critical. In particular, shock doses increase the risk of cardiovascular accidents. As mentioned above, alcohol can worsen the course of certain diseases, causing relapses or life-threatening conditions.

Alcohol consumption can also have a negative impact on a person’s already compromised health (due to previous exposure to alcohol) by affecting behaviour and lifestyle and interfering with proper medication and treatment in general.

Conclusion

Whereas direct alcohol-related mortality is registered in the official mortality statistics and can therefore be studied in some detail, studying indirect alcohol-related mortality (from external causes of death or diseases that develop because of alcohol consumption) is a research-intensive task. The most popular approaches are the population attributable fraction method, which is difficult to apply due to a lack of reliable data for analysis (especially data

on the distribution of the population by level of consumption), and the statistical analysis. In this study, we have used the time series analysis of standardised mortality rates from a range of causes of death and causes of death directly attributable to alcohol (as an indicator of alcoholisation of the population).

We have shown that alcohol (alcohol-related mortality) significantly and closely correlates with thirty causes of death in Russia, eleven of which are cardiovascular diseases. This is an important finding because cardiovascular diseases play a leading role in the structure of mortality by cause of death in Russia.

Associations were also found between alcohol and a number of various causes of death (malignant neoplasms, external causes, ill-defined causes of death, as well as tuberculosis, some diseases of the respiratory, digestive and nervous systems). These associations are consistent with the findings from epidemiological studies in other countries.

Therefore, in line with our findings, we can assume that alcohol makes a significant contribution to mortality in Russia.

Our “ecological” analysis is based on statistical associations observed at the population level. It shows the extent to which the variation in population-level mortality from different causes of death is associated with the variation in indicators of hazardous drinking. Our analysis allows to predict what changes in mortality by cause of death will occur in response to an increase or decrease in the alcohol factor. However, the causal nature of the associations between alcohol and mortality from different causes is not guaranteed, and the physiological mechanisms behind these associations are not always clear. Representative and detailed micro-level data are required to provide evidence-based causal results to reveal not only whether or not the associations exist, but also how and whom alcohol kills. Despite the significance of alcohol in the population mortality, there is a clear lack of up-to-date data in Russia on the distribution of alcohol consumption in the population, the prevalence of hazardous drinking and the associated mortality risks.

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Annex

Table A1. Spearman's correlation coefficients of SDRs for individual causes of death with causes of death directly attributable to alcohol (accidental or with undetermined intent), by sex and age-specific groups

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death	Men		Women	
		age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
Infections	Tuberculosis	.605**	0.381	.674**	-0.081
	Malignant neoplasms of lip, mouth and pharynx	-.115	0.274	.011	0.001
	Malignant neoplasms of oesophagus	-.098	-0.195	-.461*	-0.051
	Malignant neoplasms of stomach	-.270	0.031	-.039	-0.223
	Malignant neoplasms of small intestine, including duodenum	-.055	0.025	.011	0.031
	Malignant neoplasms of colon	.182	0.199	.165	0.321
	Malignant neoplasms of rectum, rectosigmoid junction, anus and anal canal	-.350	0.16	.223	0.319
	Malignant neoplasms of liver and intrahepatic bile ducts liver and intrahepatic bile ducts	.108	.485*	.440*	0.067
	Malignant neoplasms of pancreas	.219	0.269	.373	0.248
	Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined sites of the digestive system	-.051	-0.056	-.252	-0.382
Neoplasms	Malignant neoplasms of larynx	.260	-0.129	.283	0.033
	Malignant neoplasms of trachea, bronchi, lungs	-.023	0.043	-.225	-0.075
	Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined sites of the respiratory system	.308	0.23	-.115	-0.318
	Malignant neoplasms of bones, articular cartilages, extremities	-.225	-0.243	-.374	0.16
	Malignant cutaneous melanoma	.305	0.014	-.100	.425*
	Other malignant neoplasms of skin	.208	-0.062	-.081	0.107
	Mesothelioma, etc.	.180	0.398	.425*	0.084
	Malignant neoplasms of mammary gland	.240	0.137	.186	-0.011

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death	Men		Women	
		age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
	Malignant neoplasms of cervix			-.369	-0.065
	Malignant neoplasms of uterine corpus, other and unspecified parts of the uterus			-.083	-0.083
	Malignant neoplasms of ovary			.224	0.043
	Malignant neoplasms of other and unspecified female genitalia			-.064	-.430*
	Malignant neoplasms of prostate gland	.205	0.353		
	Malignant neoplasms of other male genitalia	-.555**	-.443*		
Neoplasms	Malignant neoplasms of kidneys, excl. renal pelvis	.130	0.223	.030	0.287
	Malignant neoplasms of urinary bladder	-.038	0.091	.217	-0.163
	Malignant neoplasms of other and unspecified urinary organs	-.151	-.441*	-.173	-.491*
	Malignant neoplasms of meninges, cerebrum, spinal cord	.018	0.186	.329	0.043
	Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined, secondary and unspecified sites	.046	0.223	-.162	-0.103
	Leukaemia	.182		.203	
Diseases of the endocrine system	Diabetes	-.034	-0.091	-.042	-0.062
	Other diseases of the endocrine system	.164	-0.024	-.232	-0.098
Diseases of the nervous system	Other psychoses	.082	0.09	-.207	0.13
	Other disorders of the nervous system	.636**	0.06	.476*	-0.228
	Chronic rheumatic heart diseases	-.010	-0.097	.130	0.399
	Hypertensive heart disease with predominantly cardiac involvement	.569**	0.404*	.575**	0.26
Diseases of the circulatory system	Hypertensive heart disease with predominantly cardiac and kidney involvement	.116	0.317	.339	0.392
	Other and unspecified forms of hypertension	-.028	-0.034	-.177	-0.001
	Acute myocardial infarction	.053	-0.059	.265	-0.134
	Recurrent myocardial infarction	.217	.450*	.313	0.346

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death		Men		Women	
			age	age 65+	age	age 65+
			15-64		15-64	
	Atherosclerotic heart disease		.651**	0.413	.747**	0.37
	Chronic ischaemic heart disease		.704**	.627**	.680**	.430*
	Other forms of acute ischaemic heart disease		.807**	0.025	.836**	-0.158
	Pulmonary heart and pulmonary circulatory disorders		-.037	-0.213	-.090	-0.371
	Other heart diseases		.855**	.461*	.898**	0.12
	Subarachnoid haemorrhage		.531*	0.064	.086	-0.069
	Intracerebral and other non-traumatic intracranial haemorrhages		.687**	0.193	.663**	-0.118
	Cerebral infarction		.691**	.551**	.840**	.521*
	Stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction		.563**	0.336	.466*	0.37
	Other cerebrovascular diseases		.221	.686**	.275	.544**
	Atherosclerosis		.273	0.048	.037	0.082
	Other diseases of arteries, arterioles and capillaries		.243	-0.18	-.400	-0.232
	Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis, venous thromboses and embolisms		.316	0.136	-.016	-0.197
	Bacterial pneumonia		.643**	0.228	.182	-0.104
	Pneumonia, organism unspecified		.798**	0.414	.627**	0.159
	Other chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases		.475*	.440*	.181	0.29
	Suppurative and necrotic conditions of the lower respiratory tract		.635**	0.078	.447*	-0.275
	Gastric ulcer		.083	0.104	-.014	-0.244
	Duodenal ulcer		-.073	-0.081	.094	-0.151
	Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver (excl. alcoholic)		.861**	.688**	.910**	.589**
	Other diseases of liver		.609**	0.168	.691**	-0.018
	Cholelithiasis		.106	0.108	-.303	0.172

Table A2. Spearman's correlation coefficients of SDRs for individual causes of death with poisoning by alcohol (accidental or with undetermined intent), by sex and age groups

Class of causes of death	Men		Women	
	age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
Infections				
Tuberculosis	0.556**	0.485	0.199**	0.155
Malignant neoplasms of lip, mouth and pharynx	0.149	0.053	-0.047	0.221
Malignant neoplasms of oesophagus	0.135	-0.059	0.032*	0.059
Malignant neoplasms of stomach	-0.095	-0.098	0.221	-0.152
Malignant neoplasms of small intestine, including duodenum	-0.212	-0.244	-0.382	-0.153
Malignant neoplasms of colon	0.159	-0.021	-0.081	0.159
Malignant neoplasms of rectum, rectosigmoid junction, anus and anal canal	0.134	-0.053	0.129	0.242
Malignant neoplasms of liver and intrahepatic bile ducts	0.362	0.14*	0.37*	0
Malignant neoplasms of pancreas	0.299	0.244	0.099	0.285
Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined sites of the digestive system	-0.266	-0.232	-0.547	-0.332
Malignant neoplasms of larynx	0.126	-0.05	0.014	0.088
Malignant neoplasms of trachea, bronchi, lungs	-0.09	-0.393	-0.17	0.081
Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined sites of the respiratory system and chest	0.09	0.075	-0.005	-0.224
Malignant neoplasms of bones, articular cartilages, extremities, other and unspecified sites	-0.193	-0.301	-0.287	-0.187
Malignant cutaneous melanoma	0.308	0.134	-0.05	0.352*
Other malignant neoplasms of skin	-0.226	-0.11	-0.017	0.117
Mesothelioma, etc.	0.149	0.333	0.344	0.082
Malignant neoplasms of mammary gland	0.002	-0.147	0.19	0.155
Malignant neoplasms of cervix			0.003	0.048

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death	Men		Women	
		age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
Neoplasms	Malignant neoplasms of uterine corpus, other and unspecified parts of the uterus			-0.202	0.29
	Malignant neoplasms of ovary			0.101	0.239
	Malignant neoplasms of other and unspecified female genitalia			-0.324	-0.477*
	Malignant neoplasms of prostate gland	0.006	-0.116		
	Malignant neoplasms of other male genitalia	-0.484**	-0.477*		
	Malignant neoplasms of kidneys, excl. renal pelvis	0.126	0.047	0.191	0.456
	Malignant neoplasms of urinary bladder	0.171	-0.027	0.234	0.098
	Malignant neoplasms of other and unspecified urinary organs	-0.248	-0.561*	-0.384	-0.552*
	Malignant neoplasms of meninges, cerebrum, spinal cord, cranial nerves and other parts of the nervous system	0.138	0.062	0.221	0.305
	Malignant neoplasms of other and ill-defined, secondary and unspecified sites (incl. thyroid gland)	-0.191	-0.155	-0.247	-0.174
Diseases of the endocrine system	Leukaemia	0.135	-0.214	0.251	0.005
	Diabetes	0.15	-0.014	0.242	0.095
Diseases of the nervous system	Other diseases of the endocrine system. eating and metabolic disorders	0.217	0.173	0.027	0.051
	Other psychoses	0.056	0.152	-0.202	0.385
	Other disorders of the nervous system	0.517**	-0.011	0.426*	0.164
	Chronic rheumatic heart diseases	0.111	-0.223	0.047	0.48
Diseases of the circulatory system	Hypertensive heart disease with predominantly cardiac involvement	0.21**	-0.06	0.232**	0.005
	Hypertensive heart disease with predominantly cardiac and kidney involvement	0.162	0.414	0.531	0.346
	Other and unspecified forms of hypertension	-0.044	-0.062	0.203	0.081
	Acute myocardial infarction, including certain current complications following acute myocardial infarction	-0.181	-0.379	-0.017	-0.272

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death	Men		Women	
		age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
		Recurrent myocardial infarction	0.218	0.224*	0.02
Atherosclerotic heart disease	0.556**	0.325	0.487**	0.19	
Chronic ischaemic heart disease	0.633**	0.356**	0.519**	0.382*	
Other forms of acute ischaemic heart disease	0.614**	0.367	0.478**	-0.502	
Pulmonary heart and pulmonary circulatory disorders	-0.167	-0.047	-0.562	-0.304	
Other heart diseases	0.52**	0.116*	0.451**	-0.065	
Subarachnoid haemorrhage	0.387**	0.051	0.35	-0.239	
Intracerebral and other non-traumatic intracranial haemorrhages	0.814**	0.179	0.657**	0.027	
Cerebral infarction	0.444**	0.202**	0.405**	0.257*	
Stroke, not specified as haemorrhage or infarction	0.693**	0.394	0.722*	0.427	
Other cerebrovascular diseases	0.099	0.447**	0.078	0.608**	
Atherosclerosis	0.438	0.217	0.439	0.341	
Other diseases of arteries, arterioles and capillaries	-0.209	-0.116	-0.42	-0.199	
Phlebitis and thrombophlebitis, venous thromboses and embolisms	0.014	0.023	-0.016	0.057	
Bacterial pneumonia	0.814**	0.125	0.265	0.227	
Pneumonia, organism unspecified	0.678**	0.373	0.373**	0.37	
Other chronic obstructive pulmonary diseases	0.639*	0.427*	0.433	0.516	
Suppurative and necrotic conditions of the lower respiratory tract	0.776**	0.107	0.633	0.081	
Gastric ulcer	-0.048	0.06	-0.187	-0.162	
Duodenal ulcer	-0.268	0.164	-0.017	-0.044	
Fibrosis and cirrhosis of liver (excl. alcoholic)	0.538**	0.417**	0.384**	0.349**	
Other diseases of liver	0.502**	0.119	0.361**	0.142	

Class of causes of death	Title of cause of death	Men		Women	
		age 15-64	age 65+	age 15-64	age 65+
		Diseases of the digestive system	0.085	0.099	-0.003
	Cholelithiasis	-0.212	0.062	-0.149	0.026
	Cholecystitis	0.584**	0.099	0.396**	0.27
	Acute pancreatitis and other diseases of pancreas	0.244	0.02	0.144	0.274
	Chronic nephritic syndrome (Chronic: glomerular disease, glomerulonephritis, nephritis)	0.364	0.062	0.387	0.428
	Other renal tubulo-interstitial diseases	0.396**	0.101*	0.194*	0.302*
	Other diseases of the digestive system	0.675**	0.534**	0.504**	0.489*
Symptoms, signs and abnormalities	Symptoms and other ill-defined causes of death	0.556**	0.485	0.199*	0.155
	Falls	0.149	0.053	-0.047	0.221
	Drowning	0.135*	-0.059**	0.032	0.059
	Accidental inhalation and ingestion causing obstruction of respiratory tract, foreign objects	-0.095**	-0.098**	0.221**	-0.152*
	Accidents caused by exposure to smoke, fire and flames	-0.212	-0.244	-0.382	-0.153
	Other intentional self-harm (including suicide)	0.159*	-0.021	-0.081	0.159*
External causes of death	Homicide (assault, violence) by another person, including legal execution	0.134	-0.053	0.129	0.242
	Accidental poisoning by and exposure to narcotics and psychodysleptics [hallucinogens], not elsewhere classified	0.362	0.14	0.37	0
	Intentional self-harm (including suicide)	0.299**	0.244*	0.099*	0.285
	Injuries with undetermined intent (accidental or intentional)	-0.266	-0.232	-0.547	-0.332
	Traffic accident	0.126	-0.05	0.014	0.088
	Other and unspecified traffic accidents	-0.09	-0.393	-0.17**	0.081
	Other and unspecified external causes of death and sequelae				

Note: * The correlation is significant at the level 0.05 (two-way); ** The correlation is significant at the level 0.01 (two-way).